

From Birmingham to the West Midlands: Scaling up climate risk and vulnerability mapping

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Summary

The climate is changing, and local authorities must respond to changing climate risks to protect citizens. However, not everyone is affected equally by climate change among or within regions. Following the successful publication of Birmingham's Climate Risk and Vulnerability Assessment (CRVA) maps, the CRVA mapping is being expanded and adapted for the wider West Midlands Combined Authority area, which covers seven local authorities, including Birmingham. This paper presents the progress in the methodological approach to CRVA mapping, including the new approach for mapping vulnerability, as the map is redesigned from a local (Birmingham) to regional (West Midlands) decision-making context.

KEYWORDS: climate change; climate risk and vulnerability; adaptation; climate action; geospatial analysis

1. Introduction

As the global climate is changing (IPCC, 2021) there is global inequity in how and the extent by which people are affected. This is because not only climate hazards, but socioeconomic and environmental decisions, both past and present affect people's vulnerability to the impacts of climate change differently – such as decisions that influence land use, inequity, marginalisation and governance (IPCC, 2022). To deliver effective policy with a more equitable response to climate risk, decision-makers require tools that identify and help prioritise interventions with climate-resilient place-making at its forefront. Using GIS can support this and help bring together multiple geospatial datasets pertaining to climate risk and vulnerability to support the prioritisation, targeting, and planning of climate change adaptation.

This paper summarises the approach to scaling up CRVA mapping from Birmingham, UK to the West Midlands; namely, the boundary of the West Midlands Combined Authority (WMCA). Birmingham City Council (BCC) has increased focus on delivering a more sustainable city for its residents in recent years. This led to the CRVA mapping co-development between BCC and the University of Birmingham; building on Birmingham's Environmental Justice Index (Sultan et al., 2023) and prototype research mapping heat vulnerability (Ferranti et al., 2023). In 2023, BCC published CRVA map outputs (BCC, 2023) and submitted to the Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP) which assesses organisations' commitments to bold climate action as well on transparency and leadership. As a result, BCC received its first A-grade by CDP in 2023.

Since the publication of the West Midlands' latest adaptation plan, WMCA recognise that more action

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is needed to address and respond to climate risks across the region’s communities and built environment – particularly regarding more extreme heat and flooding events, poor air quality, and the consequences to public health and widening inequality (Sustainability West Midlands, 2021). WMCA is now engaged in CRVA mapping development, focusing on three strands of work: (i) improving the dimensions of vulnerability in CRVA mapping, (ii) developing and testing a CRVA mapping approach for transport infrastructure, and (iii) engaging with a West Midlands citizens panel to optimise CRVA-related communication with the public both transparently and effectively. This paper focuses on progress regarding the first strand and briefly outlines the second.

2. Methodological approach

The CRVA mapping developed for Birmingham comprised eleven primarily open-source datasets, which were aligned, scaled to a score range between 0 and 1 (the closer to 1, the higher the risk/vulnerability), then summed without weighting via raster algebra. Greenham et al. (2023) provide details of the datasets and the GIS process undertaken for Birmingham, which consider data on temperature (Met Office, 2022), flood risk (Environment Agency, 2022a, 2022b), air quality (updates of Zhong et al., 2021), built environment (Demuzere et al., 2019), green space (Ordnance Survey, 2022a, 2022b; Environment Agency, 2022c), and social vulnerability (Ministry of Housing, Communities & Local Government, 2019; Public Health England, 2018). Initial outputs were at 100m grid resolution and then aggregated to other boundaries e.g., Parliamentary Constituencies, Wards, Lower Super Output Areas (LSOAs) for high-level decision-making. The 100m outputs are also useful at smaller development scales, whereby planners can consult them to review design proposals, ensuring they consider climate change appropriately. Figure 1 shows example CRVA map outputs for Birmingham.

Figure 1 The CRVA map for Birmingham at: a) 100m resolution (showing Parliamentary Constituency boundaries), b) LSOA boundaries, and c) Ward boundaries.

An important feature of this CRVA mapping approach was stakeholder collaboration from inception, such as BCC’s urban planners, environmental specialists, and geospatial data team. This is because the intended outcome was to empower and increase technical capacities of decision-makers through a replicable working example. As such, the authors consider the CRVA map outputs to be a ‘Minimum Viable Product’ (MVP). By collaborating with WMCA, the MVP underwent its first cycle of improvements, akin to treating adaptation as an iterative process in an organisation (Quinn et al., 2018). It enables the focus on a decision-centric approach as opposed to science-first; which can better address deep uncertainty regarding future climate change (Ranger et al., 2013) and enables WMCA to own the CRVA mapping process going forward for monitoring and evaluation purposes.

The methodological approach required modifying to improve the vulnerability aspect of the West Midlands CRVA map outputs. For the Birmingham CRVA maps, the key vulnerability layers were the Indices and Multiple Deprivation (IMD) and Excess Years' Life Lost (EYLL), while the remaining nine datasets were namely indicators of climate hazards. The resolution of both vulnerability layers was coarse relative to the hazard layers and did not sufficiently represent the spatial range of vulnerability at more localised levels. Consequently, two key adjustments to the methodology were undertaken while building the West Midlands CRVA map outputs. Firstly, additional data were incorporated from the latest 2021 UK Census data as well as income data provided by WMCA to increase the spatial dimensions of vulnerability to climate change. These provided higher resolution vulnerability layer outputs pertinent to housing, demographics, employment, income, expenses, health, and education. These were also used to generate an exposure layer as a function of population density. Secondly, the processing of these data was revised to frame risk as the product of hazards, vulnerability, and exposure (IPCC, 2022). The datasets were compiled into three layers representing these dimensions of risk, which, when multiplied together using raster algebra, produced a map of final CRVA risk scores relative to the West Midlands, with an aggregated example by LSOAs shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Development of the CRVA map for the West Midlands, with a draft output by LSOA boundaries.

The CRVA mapping approach is also being applied to the transport sector of the West Midlands and considers the exposure of transport networks and nodes to climate related hazards alongside infrastructure criticality and asset vulnerability (Hawchar et al., 2020). Therefore, the conceptual approach is similar, but considers different variables; also utilising primarily open-source data and standard GIS tools such that the process can be owned and managed by WMCA and TfWM in future for periodic updates. Figure 3 shows the draft progress of this combined CRVA mapping approach for transport across the West Midlands.

Figure 3. Draft CRVA map output for transport across the West Midlands at 100m resolution.

3. Expected results and forward look

The expected results from this project are map outputs hosted by WMCA as a climate communication tool for citizens and interested parties. Key differences to these outputs compared to the Birmingham CRVA maps shown in Figure 1 are that they (i) capture an improved dimension of vulnerability in the context of climate risk, (ii) introduce exposure to climate risk as a function of population density, and (iii) have improved underlying data resolution, leading to improved spatial accuracy of climate risk. Results are readily aggregated by administrative boundaries such as LSOAs or Wards, ranking mean climate risk scores and highlighting those with a large share of at-risk areas.

With the support of WMCA, these CRVA mapping outputs will be presented to the public via a citizens panel. It provides the opportunity for the methodological approach to be reviewed and validated through the lens of those who are most directly affected by the decisions which the WMCA can make in utilising the CRVA maps. Citizens are invited to provide feedback on the appropriate scale and resolution of the CRVA maps for effective communication purposes. The feedback will enable future improvements of the CRVA mapping process and outputs for decision makers within the WMCA, but also for other organisations who may consider adopting this approach.

Regarding the transport CRVA mapping, WMCA and TfWM are actively engaged in the development process. Their involvement ensures that outputs are fit for purpose for transport specialists across the West Midlands so that they continue to benefit stakeholders when future CRVA mapping output ownership and management is handed to WMCA.

4. Conclusions

Local and regional authorities require tools that support decision-making to protect citizens from the impacts of future climate change. Using the described methodological approach, CRVA maps were produced for Birmingham and are in progress for the West Midlands, showing the extent of inequity of climate risk and vulnerability. Engaging with relevant stakeholders from the study inception resulted in positive outcomes for BCC via increased technical capacity to address climate change, but also in its global reputation as a leading city on bold and transparent climate action. It is expected that similar outcomes are possible for the wider West Midlands region, as the MVP approach develops into a more relevant and accessible tool for stakeholders as part of iterative climate change adaptation planning.

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Biographies

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Nick Grayson, now retired, was the Green City Manager at Birmingham City Council and a Senior Research Fellow at the University of Birmingham. He led work on the strategic planning of green infrastructure and natural capital for Birmingham and contributed to research on urban air quality and green infrastructure across the West Midlands.

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